

Comparative Study of Efficacy of Corticosteroid versus Analogues Platelet Rich Plasma Injection in the Management of Plantar Fasciitis in North Karnataka Population

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic plantar fasciitis is a painful pathological condition of the foot and a challenge for the clinician to manage or treat successfully.

Method: Out of 90 (ninety) patients, 45 patients were injected with corticosteroid (2 ml, 8 mg) along with 0.5 ml of plain 2% xylocaine using a 20G wide-bore needle. PRP is prepared by drawing blood from the cubital vein with the help of BD vacutainer eclipse in three BD vacutainer tubes, which are 2.7 ml tubes that contain 0.35 ml of 3.2% sodium citrate as an anticoagulant. Blood was centrifuged twice, first at 1200 rpm and then at 2400 rpm. The platelets were checked randomly by a pathologist using Neubauer's chamber method or an auto analyzer. PRP was injected at the tenderness site after injecting 2% xylocaine with a 20-gauge needle and following up for a week, 6th week, 3rd month, and 6th month.

Results: VAS of PRP was 2.62 in PRP, 1.92 in Corticosteroid group at 6th weeks, 1.94 VAS in PRP, 2.84 in corticosteroid group at 3rd month, 1.42 VAS in PRP group, and 3.75 in corticosteroid group was observed. In comparison, AOFAS scores in both groups at different intervals had a significant p value ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: In the present study, it is concluded that corticosteroid therapy is more effective for short-term relief, but PRP therapy is more effective for long-term relief.

Keywords: platelet-Rich Plasma, Corticosteroid, 2% Xylocaine, 20 Gauge Needle, Plantar Fasciitis.

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Introduction

Plantar fasciitis is a syndrome that results from repeated trauma to the plantar fascia at its origin on the calcaneus bone. Plantar fasciitis is a common cause of heel pain and is the result of the degenerative process of plantar fascia at calcaneal attachment. The predisposing factors are age, obesity, excessive weight bearing, and tight Achilles tendon [1].

Plantar fasciitis presents in a most characteristic manner, including gradual onset and worsening with time pain in the morning on rising from the rest and localization over the medial slip of the origin of the fascia [2]. Methods of treatment include use of insoles, modification of shoes, stretching, physiotherapy, ice or cold, NSAIDs, analgesics, shock wave therapy, and immobilization [3,4]. If not responded, local corticosteroid and/or analogue platelet-rich plasma were injected locally in the management of chronic plantar fasciitis. It is

suggested that platelet-rich blood given locally is more effective than corticosteroid. Hence, an attempt is made to compare the efficacy of both drugs in adults of both sexes.

Material and Method

90 (seventy) patients aged between 25 and 60 years visited the orthopedic department of Khaja Banda Nawaz University, Faculty of Medical Sciences Kalaburgi, Karnataka 585104, were studied.

Inclusive Criteria: The patients diagnosed with plantar fasciitis by clinical and radiological evaluation presenting a complaint of plantar heel pain for more than 6 weeks (>6 weeks) and plantar fascia thickness > 4 mm at the area of maximum tenderness (USG of heel for plantar fascia) were selected for study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with severe anemia and thrombocytopenia, immune compromised patients, and non-cooperative patients were excluded from the study.

Method: Out of 90 patients, 45 were given corticosteroids (2 ml, 8 mg) and 45 were given PRP. Depomedrol injection along with 0.5 ml of plain 2% xylocaine using 20 G wide bore needles into the point of maximum tenderness Post injection, patients were asked to rest for 15 minutes and then allowed to walk.

PRP preparation and administration: For the preparation of PRP, blood was withdrawn from the cubital vein with the help of a BD vacutainer eclipse in three BD vacutainer tubes, each 2.7 ml and containing 0.5 ml of 3.2% sodium citrate, an anticoagulant, and a volume of approximately 2.35 ml for whole blood. It was prepared using a 2-spin technique in the 1st low spin step; blood is centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 10 minutes in a routine 380 R centrifuge model (Hettich, Zentrifugen). After the formation of three layers (a bottom layer of RBC, an upper layer composed of plasma, platelets, and some WBS, and an intermediate layer, or Buffy coat, composed mostly of WBC). The upper layer just above the Buffy coat was collected with a 10 ml syringe; this collection was performed carefully to avoid disturbing the bottom layer of RBC and the Buffy coat layer. Depending on the centrifugal force of the spin, the collected volume ranged from 0.75 ml to 1.25 ml in each BD vacutainer. Approximately 1 ml of the upper layer of the sample that underwent the first spin step was collected and transformed into one empty tube (approximately 3 ml). The tube was centrifuged again for 10 minutes at 2400 rpm. The upper half of the plasma volume, platelet poor plasma (PPP), was removed. The remaining volume of PRP was used for injection. The platelet count was estimated by the pathologist. The PRP was randomly checked for the number of platelets by Neubauer's chamber or auto analyzer. Most of the sample had a platelet count greater than 1,000,000/l in a 5 ml volume, which is five times the baseline. After this, the PRP is shaken by just turning the tube 2 to 3 times to mix the platelets.

PRP injection technique: patients were asked to resume supine positions, and the involved foot was cleaned and prepared with spirit and povidone iodine. The site of maximum tenderness, i.e., the medial aspect of the foot at the origin of the plantar fascia, was marked using a marker. One ml of 2% plain xylocaine was infiltrated into the skin and subcutaneous tissue. Dry needling, also called peppering, was used to locally "injure" the soft tissue to stimulate the inflammatory response. The concomitant delivery of the PRP then modulates (enhances) the healing response. Each masking point of tenderness is penetrated with a 20 G-gauge needle until the underlying periosteum is touched. A

gristly, crunchy texture is audibly and palpably noted as the needle is advanced. After contacting the periosteum, the needle was gently partially withdrawn and then advanced in a fan-like wheel (peppering) the area 7 to 10 times. Next, 1 ml of the PRP is injected as this peppering maneuver is continued. This process is then carried out at each marked site.

Post-injection care: post-injection, patients were asked to rest for 15 minutes and then allowed to walk. As PRP effectively induces an inflammatory response, some patients experienced minimal to moderate discomfort following the injection, which usually lasts for up to a week. They are instructed to ice the injected area if needed for pain control and modify activity as tolerated. Acetaminophen was the optional analgesic, and NSAIDs were avoided. After 48 hours, patients were given a standardized stretching protocol to follow for two weeks. Patients were advised to avoid strenuous activities and rest for two weeks. No aggressive running or jumping activities were allowed for 2 weeks. After 4 weeks of the procedure, patients were allowed to proceed with normal sporting or recreational activities as tolerated. Any type of foot orthosis was not advised. Each patient was assessed functionally using American orthopedic foot and ankle scores (AOFAS), visual analog scale (VAS) scores, and radiologically by ultrasound thickness of the plantar fascia. The AOFAS and VAS scores were recorded before treatment and at follow-up visits scheduled at 6 weeks, 3rd months, and 6 months.

The duration of the study was from April 2022 to March 2024.

Statistical Analysis: Clinical manifestations comparison, VAS, AOFAS, and pain severity were studied by using the t test and percentage. The statistical analysis was done in SPSS software. The ratio of males and females was 2:1.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Clinical manifestations of patients with chronic plantar fasciitis

- Right heel: 26 (57%) PRP group, 27 (60%) corticosteroid group,
- Left heel: 19 (42.2%) PRP group, 18 (40%) corticosteroid group
- VAS Baseline score: 7.17 in PRP group, 7.33 in corticosteroid group,
- Baseline AOFAS score: 53 (\pm 4.8) in PRP group, 55.4 (\pm 3.26) in corticosteroid group.
- Thickness of plantar fascia (mm): 5.72 in PRP group, 5.60 in corticosteroid group.

Table 2: Comparative study of VAS in both groups score –

- Pre-treatment PRP group: 7.15 in PRP

- group, 7.22 in corticosteroid group.
- 6 Weeks: 2.62 in PRP group, 1.92 in corticosteroid group.
- 3 months: 1.94 in PRP group, 2.84 in corticosteroid group.
- 6 months: 1.42 in PRP group, 3.72 in corticosteroid group.

Table 3: Comparison of pain sensitivity in both groups

- No pain: VAS-o had 8 (17.7%) in PRP and zero in corticosteroid group.
- In Mild pain: (1,2,3) in 6th weeks 21 (46.5%) were steroid group, 37 (82.2%) were PRP group, In 3rd month 31 (68.8%) in steroid group, 17 (37.7%) in PRP group. In 6th month 29 (64.4%) in PRP group, 9 (20%) in steroid group.
- In VAS 4, 5, 6 (Moderate pain): 13 (28.8%) were steroid group, 9 (20%) were PRP group, at 6th week 24 (53.3%) were steroid group, 8

(17.7%) were PRP group. At 3rd month 8 (17.7%) were steroid group, 28 (62.2%) were PRP group. At 6th month 7 (15.5%) were PRP group, 35 (77.1%) were steroid group.

- In Severe pain (VAS 7, 8, 9): 28 (62.2%) were steroid group, 35 (77.7%) were PRP group

Table 4: Comparison of AOFAS score in both groups –

- In Pretreatment: 54 (± 4.8) were PRP group, 57.2 (± 3.20) were corticosteroid group, t test 3.72 and p<0.001.
- At 6th weeks: 79.4 (± 2.36) in PRP group, 86.8 (± 1.34) in corticosteroid group, t test 18.2 and p<0.001
- At 3rd months: 86.56 (± 2.14) in PRP group, 79.44 (± 1.82) in corticosteroid group, t test value 17 and p<0.001
- At 6th months: 88.08 (± 3.14) in PRP group, 72.64 (± 3.14) in corticosteroid group, t test 23.4 and p<0.001.

Table 1: Clinical Manifestations of patients with chronic plantar fasciitis (No. of patients: 90)

Sl No	Manifestations	PRP group (45)	Corticosteroid Group (45)
1	Right heel	26 (57.1%)	27 (60%)
2	Left heel	19 (42.2%)	18 (40%)
3	VAS Base line score	7.17	7.33
4	Base line of AOFAS	53 (± 4.8)	55.4 (±3.26)
5	Thickness of plantar fascia (in mm)	5.72	5.60

Figure 1: Clinical Manifestations of patients with chronic plantar fasciitis

Table 2: Comparison of Visual Analogue score (VAS) in both groups

Visual score	PRP group (45)	Corticosteroid Group (45)
Pre treatment	7.15	7.22
6 Weeks	2.62	1.92
3 months	1.94	2.84
6 months	1.42	3.75

Figure 2: Comparison of Visual Analogue score (VAS) in both groups

Table 3: Comparison of pain severity in both groups

VAS	Pre treatment		6 th week		3 rd month		6 th month	
	Steroid (%)	PRP (%)	Steroid (%)	PRP (%)	Steroid (%)	PRP (%)	PRP	Steroid
No pain VAS-0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6 (17.7%)	0
Mild pain VAS 1, 2, 3	0	0	21 (46.3%)	37 (82.2%)	31 (68.8%)	17 (37.7%)	29 (64.4%)	9 (20%)
Moderate pain VAS 4, 5 6	13 (28.8%)	9 (20%)	24 (53.3%)	8 (17.7%)	7 (17.7%)	28 (62.2%)	7 (15.5%)	35(77.1%)
Severe pain VAS- 7 8,9	28 (62.2%)	35 (77.7%)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Worst pain VAS – 10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

PRP = Platelet Rich Plasma, VAS = Visual Analogue Scale

Figure 3: Comparison of pain severity in both groups

Table 4: Comparison of AOFAS score in both groups

AOFAS score	PRP Group (45) Mean (SD±)	Corticosteroid group (45) Mean (SD±)	t test	p value
Pre-treatment	54 (±4.80)	57.2 (±3.20)	3.72	p<0.001
6 Weeks	79.4 (±2.36)	86.8 (±1.54)	18.2	P<0.001
3 Months	86.56 (±2.14)	79.44 (±1.82)	17	P<0.001
6 Months	88.8 (±3.14)	72.64 (±3.10)	23.4	P<0.001

AOFAS = American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society Score, PRP = Platelets Rich Plasma

Figure 4: Comparison of AOFAS score in both groups

Discussion

In the present comparative study of the efficacy of corticosteroids versus analogues of PRP injection in the management of chronic plantar fasciitis in the north Karnataka population, in the clinical manifestations study, the right heel was 26 (57.1%) in PRP, 27 (60%) in the steroids group, and the left heel was 19 (42.2%) in PRP, 18 (40%) in the steroids group. VAS baseline score was 7.17 in the PRP group and 7.33 in the steroid group. Baseline of AOFAS 53 (± 4.8) in PRP group, 55.4 (± 3.26) in steroid group. Thickness of the plantar fascia (mm): 5.72 in the PRP group, 5.60 in the steroid group (Table 1).

In the comparison during pre-treatment, 7.15 in PRP group, 7.15 in PRP group, and 7.22 in steroid group. At 6th week, 2.62 in PRP group, 1.92 in steroid group, At 3rd month, VAS was 1.94 in the PRP group and 2.82 in the steroid group. At 6th month, 1.42 VAS in PRP group, 3.72 at steroid group (Table 2). Mild pain VAS 1, 2, 3 were 29 (64.4%) in the PRP group, and 9 (20%) in steroid was noted at 6th months. Moderate pain 4, 5, 6 was 7 (15.5%) in the PRP group, and 35 (77.1%) in the steroid group was observed at 6th months. Severe pain VAS 7, 8, 9 was observed 28 (62.2%) in the PRP group, 35 (77.7%) in the steroid group, and observed only in pretreatment (Table 3). Compari-

son of AOFAS scores at different intervals had a significant p value ($p < 0.001$) (Table 4). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7].

Plantar fasciitis is considered an overuse injury, and such a patient's history will typically reveal some combination of either intrinsic or extrinsic factors that contribute to the development of the injury. Extrinsic factors are due to unyielding surfaces on exercise (movement) and improper and excessively worn footwear [8]. Intrinsic factors include obesity, foot structure, reduced plantar flexion strength and reduced flexibility of the plantar flexor muscles, and tensional mal-alignment of the lower extremity [9]. The most common cause of plantar fasciitis is excessive pronation (inversion) of the foot. Increased tension placed arch lowering during standing and walking.

The non-surgical management for the treatment of the symptoms and discomfort associated with plantar fasciitis is (1) reducing pain and inflammation (2) reducing stress to tolerate level (3) restoring muscle strength and flexibility involved tissue. Corticosteroid local injection gives sudden relief for pain and inflammation but also reduces stress and tolerates and restores muscle strength. PRP proved to be efficient because it enables cell proliferation, angiogenesis, and cell migration to be

stimulated, resulting in tissue regeneration. Platelets secrete anti-microbial peptides, suggesting an antibiotic effect [10]. Moreover, PRP has anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects as well. It is also reported that PRP is superior to hyaluronic acid and viscosity supplementation because PRP is a biological product [11].

Hence, PRP has a multi-potential application in orthopedics and sports medicine. While corticosteroid has many side effects on prolonged usage, like osteoporosis, loss of immunity and even addiction to steroids are also recorded.

Summary and Conclusion

In the present comparative study of PRP and corticosteroids in the management of chronic fasciitis, it was confirmed that PRP injection is an efficient and safe therapeutic option for the treatment of chronic plantar fasciitis, but long-term treatment has to be the protocol to get satisfactory results. But this study demands further histopathological, nutritional, genetic, and musculoskeletal studies.

Because, despite many contributing factors, none of these factors have proven to be predictive of clinical outcome, plantar fasciitis occurs at any age in both sexes and in many occupations.

Limitation of study: Owing to tertiary location of research center, small number of patients and lack of latest techniques we have limited finding and results.

This research work was approved by Ethical committee of Khaja Banda Nawaz university faculty of Medical Sciences Kalaburgi, Karnataka 585104.

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